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Bringing “Context” to Entrepreneurship Education

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In 2012, Gallup-Silatech’s joint publication used an exciting title, ‘Qatar’s rising entrepreneurial spirit’. Almost every week we come across a program or event related to entrepreneurship in Doha. Indeed, the past few years have witnessed the fast paced rise and thickening of Qatar’s entrepreneurship ecosystem. Qatar’s rising entrepreneurial spirit has involved frequent events, training programs, and the participation of multiple actors all collaborating in the virtuous goal of raising new Qatari entrepreneurs to the realization of Qatar National Vision 2030.

The objective of this short opinion piece is to spark some discussion on the embedded nature of entrepreneurship education. The discussion centers on the premise that entrepreneurship (and its education) is an embedded process and bringing “context” to entrepreneurship education is important. Although an “entrepreneur” is inherently an “individual,” providers and educators of entrepreneurship should be cognizant of the forms of sociality, spatiality, community as well as the various norms, codes, and symbols that define cultural traits.

Entrepreneurship (and its education) is an embedded process and bringing “context” to entrepreneurship education is important.

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A second aim is to share some recent initiatives from Qatar’s dynamic entrepreneurship ecosystem and its evolution. Global economic, social and environmental challenges are rapidly growing and changing. Entrepreneurship, however, can potentially overcome the diverse nature of these challenges. Businesses can no longer afford to operate with profit, alone, as their main goal. With the introduction of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, companies all over the world are beginning to find innovative ways to integrate the SDGs into their businesses. Entrepreneurship education can potentially inspire individuals to found businesses that purely operate based on the SDGs. This is essential, as investments are being directed more towards innovative entrepreneurs who find profitable solutions that address the SDGs.

There are several reasons why the entrepreneurship sector is moving to the forefront of the global development agenda.

Some of society’s most critical issues like the SDGs can no longer be targeted by NGOs and nonprofit organizations alone because of the limited resources available. Businesses, however, have the resources to offer scale solutions for great impact. Achieving the SDGs will require collaboration across sectors, businesses and entrepreneurs devoted to enhancing the human experience for all societies.

Societies determine whether or not a business is successful and today, people will no longer settle to do business with social enterprises that are not guided by a moral compass, such as the SDGs. This is because the world needs sustainability. Now, enterprises must be engrained with a sense of responsibility towards communities. With businesses being held accountable for their actions towards the environment and societies, entrepreneurs are finding ways to make profit in innovative and creative ways. Entrepreneurship education aims to guide and inspire individuals to serve communities worldwide and speed up the progress towards the Global Goals in a profitable way.

In this issue brief, entrepreneurship will be defined and the authors will argue that entrepreneurs would benefit from being both global and local. The authors will further highlight how studying forms of embeddedness for entrepreneurship and its education in Qatar supports the Qatar National Vision 2030 and its development goals with local examples of how that has been done. Later the authors will explore different entrepreneurship education policies around the world and compare them with policies in Qatar. They will then discuss Qatar’s global ranking in terms entrepreneurship and offer recommendations in terms of education. An analysis of the entrepreneurship education for the acceleration of the Agenda 2030 for sustainable development in Africa will be explained along with an example of how an online entrepreneurship portal-platform has benefited African youth population groups. Following the analysis, the digital Senegal 2016-2025 strategy will also be analyzed as an instrument to implement the Sustainable Development Goals.

The authors will then recommend focusing on digital entrepreneurship and women entrepreneurs and offer other policy recommendations.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS AN EMBEDDED PROCESS

Entrepreneurship is a social process that is embedded in multiple non-economic realms. For instance, a common depiction of entrepreneurship rests on individual behavior. Is the individual the only agent involved in the entrepreneurship process? The answer to this question is both “yes” and “no.” The “yes” part is quite obvious, as the entrepreneur is usually the individual seeking out opportunities and identifying potentials in the environment, even in certain cases creating those opportunities. But the entrepreneurial process entails a cognitive dimension that precedes the translation of ideas into action. Entrepreneurial initiatives involve intense preparatory stages that are mentally demanding.

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Obviously the “individual” is theoretically at the center of this process; however, as this process evolves, the individual endeavor starts to connect with other structures. It is this phase in which the transformative power of entrepreneurship is revealed in its collective nature. What do we mean by the collective nature and how can we understand it more deeply?

embeddedness and by seeking to balance social justice and economic profit. This balance does not mean that entrepreneurs are less successful; community building and profit making can go hand in hand.

When the entrepreneur goes global, does it mean that local attachment is lost? I argue that being global and local at the same time could be seen as empowerment. Entrepreneurs should enjoy the spaces that are created from global to the local. Top-down, bottom-up dynamics all offer valuable opportunities to rising entrepreneurs in Qatar.

IMPLICATIONS OF EMBEDDEDNESS IN QATAR: MOVING ON...

I believe that studying forms of embeddedness for entrepreneurship and its education in Qatar supports the Qatar National Vision 2030 and its development goals. The Qatar National Vision aims at

The collective nature relates to the role of historically established societal, communal, and tribal relations as well as cultural imprints and heritage. Social embeddedness means that entrepreneurs need to be well informed about the realities and dynamics of social structures. In a sense, it is a rejection of the tendencies that individualize entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs have social objectives in addition to economic ones. Mobilizing social resources and linking them to economic resources is what entrepreneurs should do more often. In order to preserve their connection to their social roots and unleash more innovative and creative undertakings, entrepreneurs need to frame their mindsets by acknowledging social

Mobilizing social resources and linking them to economic resources is what entrepreneurs should do more often.

“transforming Qatar into an advanced country by 2030, capable of sustaining its own development and providing for a high standard of living for all of its people for generations to come” (QNV, 2008: 2). One of the key challenges identified in this document pertains to the modernization and preservation of traditions. In many ways, QNV 2030 and its human, social, environmental, and economic pillars highlight the importance of these forms of embeddedness.

This leads me to discuss an interesting event entitled “Public Policy, Entrepreneurship and Education Nexus: Promoting Qatar National Vision 2030 and Beyond” which will be hosted by Hamad Bin Khalifa University in February 7-8, 2017 in collaboration with the World Innovation Summit for Education (WISE), an initiative of Qatar Foundation. The objective of this workshop is to bring moral perspectives to entrepreneurship education. Furthermore, studying the entrepreneurship, education and policy nexus is fertile ground for uncovering the dynamics that

entrepreneurs need to embrace when it comes to mediating economic objectives—which can be quite individualistic—with social, territorial, and network embeddedness. On one hand, the workshop acknowledges the central role that entrepreneurs can play in building private sector-led dynamism, which may involve spearheading technological innovations; sustainable prosperity and development of the public and private sectors.

On the other hand, as clearly stated in the QNV 2030, it is crucial to balance modernization with tradition. Searching for the moral basis of entrepreneurship can help identify new articulations between globalization and localization, religion and capitalism, culture and markets, and, finally, between modernization and tradition. Identifying these articulations is important for bridging Qatar’s transition to a diversified, knowledge-based economy and for helping Qatar to attain global competitiveness, as expressed through Qatar’s expanding and deepening entrepreneurship ecosystem.

Searching for the moral basis of entrepreneurship can help identify new articulations between globalization and localization, religion and capitalism, culture and markets, and, finally, between modernization and tradition.

As scholars, our task is to conduct more applied research on how these processes can translate into entrepreneurship education, teaching materials, and other pedagogies.

CONCLUSIONS

To summarize, the thematic focus of the above-mentioned workshop makes a direct reference to the embeddedness of economic behavior and invites various leading intellectuals from a wide range of fields to discuss the moral bases of entrepreneurship for a fairer world. Qatar's National Vision 2030 has highlighted the importance of these embedding processes. As scholars, our task is to conduct more applied research on how these processes can translate into entrepreneurship education, teaching materials, and other pedagogies.

We need to remember that the inclusion of non-economic variables, which embed economic behavior, necessitates a deconstructing and reconstructing of the relationship between moral values and the role of the community, social institutions, economy, markets, and entrepreneurship. We can start by focusing primarily on the importance of local contexts in providing entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship Education Policies: Global Approaches, National Agendas, and the SDG Nexus

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The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are rapidly emerging as the guiding framework for both global and domestic public policy-making, in Qatar and in other countries.

There are 17 SDGs, and they have been usually considered singly, each on their own as a goal, but it is slowly being realized that their true power and inspiration comes through a nexus of mutually reinforcing goals.

For example, Goal 4 is about education: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.” The challenge becomes greater but more inspiring if we consider Goal 4 alongside Goal 5 (gender equality) and Goal 8 (sustainable and inclusive economic growth). What kind of education would support gender equality and sustainable growth? Or sustainable consumption (Goal 12), combat climate change (Goal 13), or halt biodiversity loss (Goal 15)?

As more governments try to support economic growth by fostering entrepreneurship through education, they are realizing that this has to be education for sustainability and harnessed to a nexus of SDGs, and not just one of them. The targets and indicators for [Goal 4](#) reflect this, and in particular mention (Target 4.4) entrepreneurship as part of a modern educational skill set. As Qatar continues to develop its own national programs to support entrepreneurship, a key question is what lessons (positive and negative) can be drawn from existing models?

Are there any best and worst practices? Are there any patterns to existing programs in either program design or delivery? How well are these programs doing in terms of SDGs?

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS, NATIONAL STRATEGIES

Given the importance of entrepreneurship to innovative economies, governments around the world as well as international development organizations have long supported programs in entrepreneurship education. At the international level, we have selected the following organizations: OECD, World Bank, International Labor Organization, Asian Productivity Organization, European Commission, and the United Nations. Among national governments comparable to Qatar (in size, level of economic development, or as aspirational models because of their reputed success in the field): Singapore, Malaysia, Estonia, Hong Kong, and Brunei.

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Table 1 presents a synopsis of the international and national entrepreneurship programs, categorized by sponsoring organization, program, target group and focus. Three observations jump out immediately.

First, in terms of target groups, the most favoured are gender (primarily women), and youth. Second, international organizations seem to have a wider range of programming focus, from skills training to “ecosystem support,” to access to financing. National programs are more tightly focused on skills development through education.

By “ecosystem support” we mean programs that are educational in a broader and less specifically institutionally anchored way – ones that aim at developing and supporting risk taking, an entrepreneurial culture, and ease of doing business (through lighter and streamlined regulatory regimes) that signal in some way that entrepreneurship is to be encouraged, admired, and facilitated. The third observation is that almost none of these existing programs place any significant emphasis on SDGs.

The emphasis on gender does pick up on SDG Goal 5, but usually without an explicit reference to it.

As could be expected, UNESCO’s Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) (2016-2021) aims to “support the efforts of Member States to enhance the relevance of their TVET systems and to equip all youth and adults with the skills required for employment, decent work, entrepreneurship and lifelong learning, and to contribute to the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development as a whole” (UNESCO, 2016, p. 6). The Strategy has three priority areas:

1. Fostering youth employment and entrepreneurship
2. Promoting equity and gender equality
3. Facilitating the transition to green economies and sustainable societies

Some domestic country programs (e.g., Hong Kong, Brunei) are incorporating sustainability as a feature of entrepreneurship, but it is “sustainability light”.

Table 1: Synopsis: International and National Entrepreneurship Education Programs

INTERNATIONAL

OECD		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Entrepreneurship at a Glance	SMEs	Ecosystem Support
Inclusive Entrepreneurship in Europe	Gender, Youth, Migrants, Unemployed	Ecosystem Support
Centre for Entrepreneurship, SMEs, Regions and Cities	SMEs	Ecosystem Support
HEInnovate	Higher Education	Skills, Ecosystem Support

World Bank		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
International Finance Corporation (IFC)	SMEs	Access to Finance
Gender Intelligence for Banks	Gender	Ecosystem Support
Women's Entrepreneurship Training	Gender	Skills
Women Entrepreneurship Opportunity Facility	Gender	Access to Finance
Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA)	All Ages	Ecosystem Support
Women's Entrepreneurship Finance Initiative (We-Fi)	Gender	Access to Finance

UNCTAD		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Entrepreneurship Policy Hub	Policy Makers	Database
Entrepreneurship Policy Framework and Implementation Guidance	All Ages, Educators	Skills
Empretec - Entrepreneurship Training Workshops	MSMEs, All Ages	Skills

APO		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Rural Entrepreneurship Development	Rural Entrepreneurs, Low Income	Skills
Business Models for Women Entrepreneurs	Gender	Skills

European Commission		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Entrepreneurship 2020 Action Plan	Youth	Ecosystem Support
Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp)	All Ages	Skills
Entrepreneurship Education - A Road to Success	Youth, Educators	Skills

Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
United Nations		

Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
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UNIDO		
Entrepreneurship Curriculum Programme (ECP)	Youth - Secondary	Skills

UNESCO		
Entrepreneurship Curriculum Programme (ECP)	Youth - Secondary	Skills

Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
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ILO		
Youth Entrepreneurship Programme	Youth	Skills
Know About Business (KAB)	Youth	Skills
Start and Improve Your Business (SIYB)	All Ages	Skills
Gender and Entrepreneurship Together (GET Ahead)	Gender, Low Income	Skills

NATIONAL

Singapore		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Singapore's 21st Century Competencies (21CC) Framework	Youth; Skills	Skills
Applied Learning Programme in Business and Entrepreneurship	Youth - Secondary	Skills
Young Entrepreneurs Scheme for Schools (YES! Schools)	Youth - Primary & Secondary	Skills
Action Community for Entrepreneurship (ACE)	SME	Ecosystem Support

Malaysia		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Malaysia's Education Blueprint 2013-2025	Youth	Skills
Strategic Plan on Entrepreneurship Development in Higher Education 2013-2015	Youth - Higher Education	Skills
National Entrepreneurship Framework	Youth, Low Income, Unemployed	Skills; Access to Finance
Professional Training & Education for Growing Entrepreneurs (PROTÉGÉ)	Youth	Skills
National Dual Training System	Unemployed	Skills
I-KIT Programme	Gender, Low Income	Skills

Estonia		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Estonian Entrepreneurship Growth Strategy 2014-2020	Youth	Skills
Entrepreneurship Education Program (ETTEVÕT-LUSÕPPE PROGRAMM)	Youth, Educators	Skills
Youth Entrepreneurship Development Program (ENTRUM)	Youth	Skills

Hong Kong		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
Junior Achievement Hong Kong	Youth - Secondary	Skills
School-Company-Parent Program	Youth - Secondary	Skills
MIT Innovation Academy Teaching Lab	Youth - Secondary, Educators	Skills

Brunei		
Program	Target Groups/ Sectors	Focus
National Entrepreneurship Agenda (NEA)	Youth	Skills
Entrepreneurship Village (EV)	Youth	Skills
Success Weekends	Youth - Primary & Secondary	Skills
Brunei Darussalam Entrepreneurship Education Scheme (BEES)	Youth - Secondary	Skills
LiveWIRE Brunei	All Ages	Skills, Access to Finance
Junior Achievement	Youth - Primary & Secondary	Skills

LESSONS FOR QATAR FROM INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES

Qatar’s National Vision 2030 and its first (2011-2016) and second (2018-2022) National Development Strategies (NDS) have all highlighted the importance of human capital, economic diversification, private sector development, and ultimately, of entrepreneurship. In NDS-1, three of thirteen targets were designed to strengthen the private sector and promote entrepreneurship. A principal tool was the

Qatar Development Bank, which created a portfolio of services to support companies. NDS-2 highlighted the importance of promoting a vibrant entrepreneurship and innovation culture, especially among Qatari nationals (Ministry of Development Planning and Statistics (Qatar), 2018, p. 99). Specifically, it promised to: “develop programmes to encourage youth scholarships, promote entrepreneurship among Qatari youth.” It also noted the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs, despite progress since NDS-1.

Qatari policy makers recognize the importance of entrepreneurship, but at the same time they have not specifically flagged entrepreneurship education as a target and tool of policy.

It is clear that in NDS-2 Qatari policy makers recognize the importance of entrepreneurship, but at the same time they have not specifically flagged entrepreneurship education as a target and tool of policy. More importantly, NDS-2 is fully cognizant of the SDGs and the importance of sustainability – the word is mentioned on 115 of its 337 pages.

A scan of the Qatari entrepreneurship education and support landscape shows a variety of initiatives. The Qatar Foundation, partner universities in Education City, and the Qatar Science and Technology Park (QSTP) are leading examples. In 2020, QSTP will co-host (with the European Innovation Academy) the Arab Innovation Academy. The Qatar Development Bank (QDB) is another primary government policy tool, offering programs in financing, export promotion, business support, and skills and ecosystem development. It co-sponsors the [Qatar Business Incubator](#).

Qatar University has launched a QU Entrepreneurship and Innovation Strategy, both to transform the university and to contribute to the national entrepreneurial ecosystem. Carnegie Mellon University in Qatar (CMU-Q) offers a certificate program ([“Young Entrepreneurs”](#)) for [high school students](#), and the [Bedaya Center for Entrepreneurship and Career Development](#) provides networking and advisory opportunities for Qatari youth. As in the Hong Kong and Brunei examples above, Junior Achievement is also active in Qatar through [Injaz Qatar](#), an NGO that partners with the business community to offer programs (work readiness, financial literacy, entrepreneurship) in elementary, high schools, youth centers and colleges and universities throughout Qatar (see the case study of Injaz in Greene, Brush, Eisenman, Neck, & Perkins, 2015).

The results have been impressive. The 2018 Global Entrepreneurship Index lists Qatar as first in the Arab region and 22nd globally (out of 137 countries) (Ács, Szerb, & Lloyd, 2017).

The 2018/2019 Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (with a sample of 49 countries) presents several positive findings for Qatar (Bosma & Kelley, 2018):

- It was the highest ranked countries in the MENA region for “entrepreneurship context” (consisting of 12 weighted framework conditions), and among the top three for the entire sample (with Indonesia and the Netherlands)
- It was one of only six countries with roughly equal “Total Entrepreneurial Activity” rates for men and women
- For every person starting a business in Qatar, three intend to start one in the next three years
- Among national survey respondents in Qatar, 76.7% give high status to entrepreneurs, and 68.2% consider entrepreneurship as a good career choice (as a comparator, the Republic of Korea’s results were 70% and 52% respectively)

Considering these efforts and these results in Qatar, and comparing them to the review of entrepreneurship education programs, we arrive at one major observation. The international and national cases we summarized above show extensive efforts to embed entrepreneurship in the curriculum across all education levels. However, in Qatar, the emphasis of government policy has been more on economic support, ecosystem policies, and much less on education. Government assistance has “been overseen by an economic rather than an education organization” (Greene et al., 2015, p. 89). The Qatar National Development Strategy does mention entrepreneurial skills and training, but most actual initiatives have been in business support, incubators, science and technology, etc. These are all laudable, but international best practice seems to place equal if not more emphasis on educational efforts in schools. In many countries, these efforts are expressed through a national strategy or an entrepreneurship educational framework overseen by the relevant Ministry of Education.

The Qatar National Development Strategy does mention entrepreneurial skills and training, but most actual initiatives have been in business support, incubators, science and technology, etc.

This leads us to conclude with one major recommendation, and three additional supporting ones.

Recommendation 1: The Ministry of Education and Higher Education be tasked to develop a strategy to embed entrepreneurship in mid-school through high school. Singapore, Malaysia and Brunei offer useful models. This would involve developing curricular materials as well as teaching training. Injaz Qatar provides a local model of educational-business partnership and SME mentoring that could provide a foundation for a more elaborated program.

Recommendation 2: In addition to delivery of entrepreneurship programs through the school system, Qatar could investigate online self-learning modules and resources. Digital tools have been developed through HEInnovate and the Asian Productivity Organization, and would themselves be innovative delivery channels serving a different clientele than school-age youth.

Recommendation 3: Qatar has an opportunity to develop unique and distinctive programs to support education for social entrepreneurship. Most national and international programs focus on for-profit business, but given Qatar's Islamic heritage and emphasis on charitable service, this could be a type of entrepreneurship education that could both serve the country and provide a model for others.

Recommendation 4: Qatar can be a pioneer on embedding the SDGs into entrepreneurship education. Moreover, it can take an approach that encourages an entrepreneurial, social development oriented emphasis on sustainability. Students could be encouraged to be entrepreneurs developing sustainable products and services that will contribute to the nation's development strategy as well as to its global commitments.

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Entrepreneurship Education for the Acceleration of Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development in Africa

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Across the African continent, unemployment levels remain high despite increasing levels of tertiary education. According to the United Nations, there are approximately 200 million Africans aged between 15 and 24 that make up more than half of the unemployment statistics on the continent (Ighobor, 2017). Youth make up approximately 60% of all the continent's unemployed. In countries, such as Senegal, South Africa, Botswana, this figure jumps to

approximately 30-40% while in North Africa, the rate is more than 25% (Ighobor, 2017). In most African states, youth unemployment takes place at a rate more than twice that for adults. In the majority of African states, young women are determinedly affected by unemployment than their male counterparts. In the majority of cases, it is more difficult for young women to find decent employment than their male counterparts.

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This is despite having comparable experience and skills set. In addition, Africa's youth find it even more problematic to find work in places that pay good wages, provide a measure of job security or develop skills for career development (Page, 2013). Equally important is the problem of under-employment, often masking the extent of youth unemployment in many African states which require even greater attention and government intervention in dealing with the issue (Page, 2013).

All this comes at the backdrop of continued population growth which will only aggravate an already delicate situation and ongoing policy concern facing governments across the continent. It is thought that by 2050 the continent's youth population will increase by approximately 50% (Sow, 2018). By that period, Africa is expected to house the largest number of youths globally, making up nearly twice the young population of Oceania, Southeast Asia, South Asia and East Asia (Sow, 2018).

It is predicted that the global population will have grown by approximately 2.2 billion and half of those people will be Africans. The implications on the labour force will be significant if the current population trends continue.

As the continent's youth population are set to represent an important share of Africa's total population, the risks that can arise if this young population is not given the opportunities needed to better their economic standings could be devastating and dire for their governments. Indeed, countless risks such as mass migration, insecurity and instability would need to be dealt with by African leaders while emphasis need to be placed on the need to invest into young people's skills upgrading, education to unlock innovation, productivity, thereby helping to reduce poverty and ensuring the continent's make headways in meeting their SDGs. One such training is entrepreneurship training and education.

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While entrepreneurship is accelerating among the youth on the continent, there are still several important barriers that hinder continued growth and optimum.

Entrepreneurship is increasingly viewed as an important factor for sustainable broad-based development in emerging markets given that new businesses created have the potential to accelerate innovation and introduce new competitors to existing structures, thus contributing to productivity and eventually decent employment creation as well as economic growth.

The potential of entrepreneurship to the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 8 on decent work and economic growth is undeniable and is well researched. This brief issue will examine a few important joint programs in the area of entrepreneurship education and their potential contribution to the attainment of the Agenda 2030 for sustainable development.

According to a recent study by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor in partnership with the Youth Business International, approximately 60 percent of 18 to 34-year-olds were confident about their business prospects and believed they had the skills to successfully start a business (Bosma, N and Kelley, D., 2018).

The report further showed that at 29, the continent has the highest number of young people involved in new businesses (Bosma, N and Kelley, D., 2018). While entrepreneurship is accelerating among the youth on the continent, there are still several important barriers that hinder continued growth and optimum.

Some factors range from inadequate funding, poor infrastructure and technology to networks and technical knowledge and expertise. Entrepreneurship education curriculum jointly developed and administered by technical institutes and private sector entities are increasingly viewed as central for the growth and development of the sector, particularly among the youth.

By offering practical and industry relevant information on the key concepts of enterprise development, entrepreneurship education jointly administered by multilateral institutions such as the United Nations, academia and the private sector could contribute towards creating a space where youth are more open

to entrepreneurship as a viable alternative to earning a sustainable living (Stephan, et. al, 2015).

It provides knowledge and technical know-how in terms of business plan development and aims to create an ecosystem map for corporates and start-ups, which will locate and connect various entrepreneurial service providers across the continent (Stephan, et. al, 2015). Young African entrepreneurs will have access to knowledge about how to acquire funding, implement their innovations, and network and pitch their innovative ideas.

The United Nations Development Programme in partnership with Accenture, a multinational professional services company that provides services in strategy, digital technology, consulting and operations to establish YAS!, an online entrepreneurship portal-platform gears towards African youth population groups. Its objective is to cultivate a mind-set of employment generation and individual businesses that could contribute to the continent's sustainable development

efforts in helping to realize the Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development. The online platform, which serves the entire continent, addresses for main pillars of entrepreneurship, essentially mentorship, information, network and funding. The initiative targets young entrepreneurs and start-ups as well as incubators, venture capitalists as well as private donors seeking businesses either involved in an acceleration or incubator programme as well as those requiring capital.

The benefits and impacts of YAS! Is so invaluable and could not have come at a better time for the continent and its youth population. Through resources and educational programming gears towards the youth, the initiative is promoting opportunities for some of the continent's most vulnerable and disadvantaged population group. By offering much needed information and technical knowledge on key concepts of enterprise development, initiatives such as YAS! is helping to be a continent where young people are more open to entrepreneurship as a viable alternative

Young African entrepreneurs will have access to knowledge about how to acquire funding, implement their innovations, and network and pitch their innovative ideas.

Young African entrepreneurs are now afforded an opportunity to implement their innovation, apply for financing as well as network and pitch their innovative entrepreneurial ideas and projects with potential partners and financiers.

to trying to secure formal employment in the public or private sector which is often very hard to come by given the size of African economies and the amount of people entering the job market each year. The portal provides services such as business plan development and aims to create an ecosystem map for start-ups and corporates, which will locate and connect various entrepreneurial service providers across Africa. Young African entrepreneurs are now afforded an opportunity to implement their innovation, apply for financing as well as network and pitch their innovative entrepreneurial ideas and projects with potential partners and financiers.

For a large number of young people on the continent, addressing social and economic issues, such as poverty eradicating, accessing decent employment remains a paramount issue of concern.

African governments and the private sector have and continue to struggle in creating enough decent employment for the continent's burgeoning youth population (International Labour Organization, 2017).

For decades, African youth entrepreneurs have run small-scale businesses to support their families and themselves, make a small profit and generate employment opportunities.

With the digital revolution ushering in a new and expanding wave of young entrepreneurs that seek to provide sustainable sources of livelihoods, innovative programs and projects (JA Worldwide and Citi Foundation, 2014), such as YAS! are well placed to maximize the entrepreneurship opportunities found on the continent and promises to providing the needed support services to help reduce poverty and helping governments attain Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development.

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The Digital Senegal 2016-2025 Strategy, as an Appropriate Instrument to Implement the Sustainable Development Goals. The Digital Senegal 2016-2025 Strategy

Dr. Cristina D'Alessandro, UMR PRODIG

THE DIGITAL SENEGAL 2016-2025 STRATEGY

In October 2016, Senegal published its national strategy Digital Senegal 2016-2025 (DS2025). This policy docu

ment is well thought, precise, and adapted to the Senegalese context. This strategy is in fact rooted in the previous national development strategy (Senegal Emerging Plan: SEP), adopted by the Government in November 2012, aiming at

being the baseline of every national economic and social policy for the medium and long term. As such, the SEP wants to ensure coherence and focus in policymaking. Through this development plan, the goal of Senegal is to support economic growth with a strong impact on social development and employment. In order to achieve this target, the country must reinforce its achievements in political governance and to focus on economic stability. To implement the national development plan, an important investment program in priority sectors, capable to impulse a strong and continuous growth, has been set in place.

The DS2025 strategy concentrates on one of these priority sectors. In fact, it embodies the Senegalese ambition to maintain its role of leader country in the digital sector at the continental level in Africa and more particularly in West Africa, where the country has always been considered as one of the major economies and one of the preeminent political regimes, known for its stability and development progress since Independence from France in 1960.

The slogan summarizing the digital strategy is: “digital technology available for everyone and for every purpose from 2025 in Senegal together with a dynamic and innovative private sector within an efficient ecosystem”. The total cost of the strategy, including 28 reforms and 69 projects, has been estimated to 1,361 billions of CFA francs (equivalent to 2.3 billions USD)

The strategy is based on three key prerequisites (the legal and institutional framework, human capital, and the digital asset) and four priority areas:

1. An affordable and easy access to digital networks and services
2. An administration serving citizen and enterprises through digital services
3. The support to an innovative digital industry producing value addition
4. The promotion of digital technologies in priority economic sectors.

To understand the DS2025 strategy and its chances to be successfully implemented and to produce the results expected, a clear vision of the economic and political context of Senegal is necessary.

THE ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL CONTEXT IN SENEGAL

Since 1960, Senegal has built a stable and democratic political system, based on free elections and periodic changes in political leadership. Despite some contestations and strikes, since the first election of the president Léopold Senghor, the country has never experienced any political turmoil, despite the changes of power that have taken place since the birth of the contemporary Senegalese state. The last presidential elections in

February 2019, the 11th since Independence, have given a second mandate to the president Macky Sall to continue to implement the SEP for 7 more years. The 2018 Ibrahim Index of African Governance (IIAG), measuring the quality and evolution of political governance in Africa, confirms the Senegalese political stability and the quality of democratic governance.

The IIAG ranks Senegal 10th and points out its steady progress during the last decade in every domain monitored, but more particularly in human

development. According to the IIAG report, Senegal is, together with Uganda, Chad and Capo Verde, among the countries that have registered the most important improvements in relation to access to electricity. If henceforth Senegal is a stable country from a political point of view, according to World Bank data, its economy is also among the top 10 fastest growing economies in 2018.

The country is ranked 8th at the global scale for its real GDP growth at market prices (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Fastest growing economies in 2018 according to their real GDP growth

Enhancing feminine digital entrepreneurship is going to greatly contribute to women empowerment and to social inclusion in the country [Senegal].

Furthermore, this positive economic trend that goes back at least to 2011 is sustainable, as it is rooted in a progressive improvement of the business environment in the country. The annual World Bank Ease of doing business 2020 indicates that Senegal is ranked 123 among 190 economies, constantly improving its performance since 2013, when it was ranked 178. This means that economic growth in Senegal is the result of an entrepreneurial ecosystem constantly improving over time.

Nevertheless, small-scale enterprises constitute 45.8 percent of Senegal's economic private sector, followed by medium-scale enterprises (39.4 percent). This is quite common in sub-Saharan Africa, but it is the sign of a vulnerability of the economy, dominated by small and medium enterprises, for which sustainable financing is still a serious challenge and access to reliable infrastructure and services is problematic. The diagnostic study made under the SEP has pointed out this fragility that the plan aims at resolving (Mansoor et al. 2018), also through the DS2025.

In fact, successful efforts to improve a reliable access to electricity, as indicated by the IIAG, and to enhance Internet connectivity (90 percent of the national territory being already covered by mobile phone connection) are part of the DS2025.

FOCUSING ON DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

The choice made to focus on digital entrepreneurship is based on the diagnosis made by the strategy that digital enterprises are going to increase the gross domestic product (GDP) by 10 percent by 2025, while creating 35,000 direct jobs. Furthermore, as indicated in the DS2025 (page 20), enhancing feminine digital entrepreneurship is going to greatly contribute to women empowerment and to social inclusion in the country. In fact, the strategy asserts that women's social and economic empowerment through information and communication technologies (ICT) is going to happen by giving access by

2025 to e-commerce and electronic public services to 33 percent of rural women. This is one of the major goals of the strategy.

The choice to focus on women entrepreneurship for the digital sector is based on the fact that women entrepreneurs are numerous and they are a real economic strength for the country. Women entrepreneurship has been encouraged and developed in the last decades through various development policies and projects funded through development assistance schemes, as a tool to enhance women empowerment in the country. As a matter of fact, women entrepreneurs are an important and ever growing reality in Senegal, despite the difficulties and the fact that most of their enterprises are small and financially fragile. In this context, women entrepreneurship is a “necessity”, but also a powerful social and economic game changer for the country. A number of recent initiatives have been developed in recent years to support women

entrepreneurship in Senegal: the Réseau des jeunes femmes entrepreneures and the Maison des femmes entrepreneures, both created in 2018. The existence of an [Association des femmes sénégalaises dans les TIC](#) also indicates that women entrepreneurs in the ICT are an important reality in the country, from which the strategy wants to take advantage.

DS2025: A TOOL TO IMPLEMENT THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS, WITH A FOCUS ON EDUCATION

The DS2025 strategy clearly indicates that its implementation is in line with the priority areas of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), especially when it comes to gender equality and environmental protection. The strategy states that digital technologies, especially the Internet of things (IoT) applications and machine-to-machine (M2M) communications radically transform service provision and subsequently contribute to SDGs progress.

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It is henceforth critical to transform the entire educational system (from primary education to tertiary and professional education) in line with the development and widespread use of digital technologies. To this extent, the Ministry in charge of education is reforming school programs. It is also introducing digital knowledge and information at every level of the educational system. The Ministry of tertiary education is also implementing relevant projects, including: an integrated governance system for higher education (SIGESR) and the Virtual University of Senegal. The country aims at developing distance learning and virtual platforms to attract foreign students and improve the quality of its university system. Other actions focus on modernizing school management and governance through digital technologies and training school teachers and professor to digital technologies.

Nevertheless, to achieve the goal to give access to a computer to every student and to connect to the Internet and equip 50 percent of the schools and 100 percent of the universities by 2025, according to the aim of the

strategy, lots remains to be done, especially in terms of capacities to be built.

CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The Senegalese example demonstrate the importance of having a strong national development plan, like the SEP, taking into account the resources available in the country, pointing out major gaps and deficiencies, setting out clear and realistic goals, indicating priority economic domains and opening the way to sectoral public policies to implement the plan within a precise timeline and budget. Furthermore, the national voluntary review of the SDGs realized by Senegal in 2018 (Republic of Senegal 2018) proves that the SEP is perfectly in line with the SDGs that it implements in the specific context of Senegal.

The DS2025 strategy emphasizes the critical importance of digitalization, to structurally and sustainably transform the economy and implement the SDGs.

If this is true for a developing country like Senegal, the same applies to Gulf countries still overrelying on extractive resources and still struggling to really diversify their economies, while focusing on SDGs implementation and sustainable development. Qatar E-government 2020 Strategy is for example similar to the DS2025, but it only concentrates on digital government, while the Senegalese strategy encompasses various key economic sectors (mainly agriculture, health, and education) and more precisely priority economic domains.

To this extent, the Senegalese digital strategy contributes to build productive and human capacities and a strong emphasis is given to capacity development in the DS2025, pointing out that digitalization is a critical tool to build individual and economic capacities for a country. This points out the important role of education and even more of digital education for job creation and also for implementing the SDGs through SDG8.

To conclude, the Senegalese strategy includes a precise budget and financing mechanism, indicating that 73 percent of the budget must come from the private sector, 17 percent from the public sector and 10 percent from public private partnerships (PPPs). This issue brief recommends that ad hoc policies must be set in place to ensure that the budget is available and that every stakeholder does its part, which has not to be given for granted.

The major policy recommendation that this issue brief wants to highlight is that policies, financing mechanism, political will, the educational system, and the business environment must to converge towards a common goal, which must be considered as a common and superior interest (SDGs implementation) and converging efforts must be set in place to achieve this goal. Digitalization is a critical instrument to this extent: it creates unique opportunities for individuals, societies and economics.

Policies, financing mechanism, political will, the educational system, and the business environment must to converge towards a common goal, which must be considered as a common and superior interest (SDGs implementation) and converging efforts must be set in place to achieve this goal.

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